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Artificial Intelligence And The Nigerian Criminal Justice System: Plus Or Minus For Principles Of Fairness, Justice And Ethics

Maria Chigozie Onuegbulam, PhD, BL.

**Senior Lecturer, Department of Public Law, Faculty of Law,
Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Agbani, Nigeria
E-mail: maria.onuegbulam@esut.edu.ng**

ABSTRACT

While the evolution of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has gained global recognition, its introduction into the justice sector by some jurisdictions across the globe is as commendable as it raises thought provoking legal and ethical issues of concern for legal minds. Obviously, introducing AI into the criminal justice system especially in areas of crime investigation, assignment of cases to courts, and sentencing will certainly help to fast-track justice delivery, reduce bias and decongest the system. However, while its implications could be laudable, its compatibility with principles of fairness, justice, and ethics in a fragile democracy like Nigeria may appear as remote as it could be a nightmare in the absence of compelling judicial discipline and commitment. The aim of this research is to examine whether introducing Artificial Intelligence into the Nigerian criminal justice system will be a plus or minus for principles of fairness, justice and ethics. The objective of the study is to highlight the Trinitarian principles of fairness, justice and legal ethics as top priorities within the criminal justice system and to ensure proper safeguards for the rights of suspect and victims. The question is whether the system can effectively and transparently manage the role of human involvement in AI-assisted criminal justice system, the possibilities of bias in decision-making, and deliver functional justice. To what extent can AI algorithms be relied upon in crime investigations, assignment of cases and in unbiased sentencing decisions? The goal is to foster a fair, just and transparent criminal justice within a system that embraces the benefits of AI technology without compromising the core values of criminal justice. The study adopted the doctrinal approach.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Criminal Justice system, AI Algorithms, core values of criminal justice

1. INTRODUCTION

Admittance of Artificial Intelligence Technology into the criminal justice system is a welcome development. It will go a long way to aid in speedy dispensation of justice if well managed. Obviously, the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies in various sectors and discipline has sparked hope of significant advancements, which has perhaps encouraged its application in criminal justice system, especially in areas of crime investigation, assignment of cases to courts, trials and sentencing. AI technologies, such as predictive analytics, machine learning algorithms, and data-driven decision-making, can promote the analysis of vast datasets to forecast potential criminal activities, while enabling proactive

interventions by law enforcement agencies.¹ Machine learning algorithms, evolving continually through data soft beats, hold the potential to unravel intricate legal subtlety, augmenting the overall efficacy of the criminal justice system. Within the areas of crime investigation and assignment of cases to courts, the use of artificial intelligence could help to streamline the legal process, sort out frivolous cases, expedite the distribution or selection process and pave way for more serious and urgent cases. Also within the specific domain of sentencing, AI technologies seem to present opportunities to streamline decision-making processes. Predictive analytics, for instance, seeks to predict an individual's likelihood of reoffending, potentially informing judicial decisions. Also, machine learning algorithms, trained on historical legal data, can identify patterns that may elude human observations, thereby contributing to a more refined understanding of legal contexts. Nonetheless, behind the rapid technological evolution is the complex legal and ethical concern that must be carefully examined to ensure a fair and just criminal justice system. Efficiency goals must be harmonized with an exploration of potential biases within algorithms, transparency in decision-making processes, and the arching issue of accountability. There is the fear is that the use of historical data in AI systems could pose risks of perpetuating existing biases in the criminal justice system, potentially resulting in algorithmic discrimination and negative impacts on certain statistics. It is therefore, paramount to ensure that the integration of AI aligns with principles of fairness, justice, due process and legal ethics. Striking a balance between leveraging the benefits of AI in criminal justice system in relation to sentencing for example and mitigating its risks demands a meticulous examination of its compatibility with the fundamental principle within the system. Moreover, a robust ethical foundation must guide the development and deployment of AI technologies within the criminal justice system. As, Artificial Intelligence (AI) continues its rapid evolution, there is an undeniable need to scrutinize its impact on the legal and ethical dimensions of criminal justice. For example, the position of the law on AI assisted sentencing is still ambiguous. While it is acknowledged that AI Technology may come with various advantages, it is the law rather than the exception that core values of criminal justice are not compromised. It is therefore a clarion call on all stakeholders, law enforcement agents, ministers and judges in the temple of justice to maintain effective legal standard and ethical principles that encourage fairness and justice within the criminal justice system; a system that aims at upholding justice, fairness and respect for the rights of victim and accused. Anything short of a responsible and just application of artificial intelligence in criminal justice system may lead to sharp slip that could have the potency of miscarrying justice, marring the system, and making artificial intelligence counter-productive. The research is divided into four parts. Part one introduces the work. Part two discusses Artificial Intelligence, its brief history and implications. It also highlights criminal justice system, sentencing and AI bias. Part Three examines the use of Artificial intelligence in criminal justice system its advantages and disadvantage and the compatibility of Artificial Intelligence with justice, fairness and legal ethics. Part four is the conclusion.

2. Artificial Intelligence, History and Implications

Artificial intelligence is simply a technology that makes a computer or a computer controlled robot or a software to exhibit intelligence like the human mind. Such machines are capable of performing tasks that are traditionally associated with human intelligence such as making predictions, identifying objects, interpreting speech and generating natural language. According to the International Business Machine Corporation,² it is an interdisciplinary science with multiple approaches. Since the development of digital computer in the 1940s, it has been demonstrated that computers can be programmed to carry out very complex tasks such as discovering proofs for mathematical theorems or playing chess with great

¹ Melanie Mitchell, (2024) *Artificial Intelligence: A Guide FOR Thinking Humans*.(U S A: Macmillan Publishers) Also see, Fei-Fei Li,(2024) *The World I See: Curiosity, Exploration and Discovery at the Dawn of AI* www.Amazons .com. accessed 20 August 2024.

² International Business Machine, 'What is Artificial Intelligence (AI)'³ August 2024 <https://www.ibm.com/topics/artificial-intelligence>, accessed 21 August 2024.

proficiency. Yet, despite continuing advances in computer processing speed and memory capacity, there are as yet no programs that can match full human flexibility over wider domains or in tasks requiring much daily knowledge. Nonetheless, with the launch of ChatGPT³ by Open AI in 2022, Artificial Intelligence (AI) became impactful and has continued to, significantly impact everyday lives in various forms. According to recent research, on its own or combined with other technologies⁴ AI can perform tasks that would otherwise require human intelligence or intervention. Digital assistants, GPS guidance, autonomous vehicles, and generative AI tools like Open AI's Chat GPT are just a few examples of AI in the everyday events and our daily lives. Today, the leap forward is in natural language processing (NLP). Presently, generative AI can learn and synthesize not just human language but other data types including images, video, software code, and even molecular structures⁵.

Factually, AI is not as novel as many think, although it continually undergoes diverse stages of evolution. Though Alan Turing⁶, did not comprehensively define Artificial Intelligence, but proposed a test in 1950 to determine a machine's ability to exhibit intelligent behavior. This is known as the Turing Test. It involves a human judge engaging in natural language conversations with both a human and a machine, without knowing which is which. If the judge is unable to reliably distinguish between the human and the machine based on their responses, the machine is said to have demonstrated artificial intelligence.⁷ Though Alan did not provide a concise definition for artificial intelligence, his ideas and research laid the foundation for the development of artificial intelligence as a field of study. It was John McCarthy who coined the term "Artificial Intelligence" in 1955.⁸ According to him, AI is the science and engineering of making intelligent machines, especially intelligent computer programs. It is related to the similar task of using computers to understand human intelligence, but AI does not have to confine itself to methods that are biologically observable.⁹

The World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) has defined AI as "a discipline of computer science that is aimed at developing machines and systems that can carry out tasks considered to require human intelligence, with limited or no human intervention"¹⁰. It is the theory and development of computer systems able to perform tasks normally requiring human intelligence, such as visual perception, speech recognition, decision-making, and translation between languages¹¹.

According to Encyclopedia Britannica, Artificial intelligence (AI), is the ability of a digital computer or computer-controlled robot to perform tasks commonly associated with intelligent beings. The term is frequently applied to the project of developing systems endowed with the intellectual processes characteristic of humans, such as the ability to reason, discover meaning, generalize, or learn from past experience¹². It is the intelligence of machines or software, as opposed to the intelligence of living beings,

³ Chat GPT is a Chabot and virtual assistance developed by Open AI and launched on 30 November 2022. Based on large language models, it enables users to refine and steer a conversation towards a desired length, format, style, level of details etc. It is trained to follow an instruction promptly and provide a detailed response.

⁴ E.g., sensors, geolocation, robotics.

⁵ IBM, *Ibid*.

⁶ A. Turing, "Computing Machinery and Intelligence", N: Mind, Volume 59, Number 236, pp. 433-460. (Edinburgh: Thomas Nelson & Sons, October 1950) 1. He is often referred to as the "Father of computer science",

⁷ *Ibid*.

⁸ C Manning "Artificial Intelligence Definition" <http://jmc.stanford.edu/articles/whatisai.pdf> 2020 accessed 22 February 2024.

⁹ *Ibid*.

¹⁰ *Funmirobo*, "When AI Meets Law: The Legal Implications of the use of AI Systems" <http://www.funmirobertsandco.com>, accessed 22/2/24.

¹¹ Definitions from Oxford Languages, /,ɑːtɪfɪʃl mɪ'telɪdʒ(ə)nəs/ accessed 22 February 2024.

¹² B J Copeland." Encyclopedia Britannica on artificial intelligence" accessed 22 February 2024.

mainly human beings. It is a field of study in computer science that develops and studies intelligent machines. However, intelligent this programmed robot may exhibit, AI has no real definition of intelligence to offer, not even in the subhuman case. Its intelligence does not even equal that of rat because rats are intelligent on their own.

There are other AI programs which are used in law enforcement work and in preparation and presentation of evidence at trial, including probabilistic genotyping,- predictive policing (profiling), facial recognition, and other machine-based processes. AI helps to automate the criminal justice system in various ways. It enables case management, legal research, analysis of the diverse parameters of the crime, risk assessment, development of virtual courtrooms, dispute resolution and unbiased justice to those wrongly accused as criminal especial when unbiased.

3. Criminal Justice system, Sentencing and AI Bias

Criminal Justice

Criminal justice exists for the control and prevention of crime. The criminal justice process involves all the agencies and procedures set up to manage both crimes and those accused of violating the criminal law.¹³ Criminal justice therefore, is a process that involves series of steps beginning with a complaint or information of crime commission, followed by a criminal investigation, possible arrest, prosecution processes and ending with a probable acquittal/discharge or the release of a convicted offender after serving his term or even the execution of an offender where applicable. Criminal justice takes place within the criminal justice system. Thus, criminal justice system is the collective institutions through which an accused offender passes until the accusations have been disposed of or the assessed punishment concluded. The system has three components namely, the law enforcement, the judicial process and corrections.¹⁴ A strong system aids and strengthens justice delivery. The Judicial arm within the criminal justice system- the court is saddled with the onerous task of administration of justice.

Ordinarily, without applying the law yet, everyone in the society is presumed innocent until the person commits a crime or is accused of one. But legally speaking, under the adversarial criminal justice system, it is trite that an accused is presumed innocent until proven guilty.¹⁵ It is worthy of note that the proof of an accused guilt takes place before a court of competent jurisdiction not outside the court. As such, the criminal justice system and the process are set on motion the moment a complaint is made to the police by the society or any member of the society or by the police on their own detecting the commission of a crime.¹⁶ The accused, like a product goes from station to station within the system and at each station something is done in the system and something is done to the accused. If the accused “passes” inspection, he¹⁷ moves on to the next station. Theoretically, if the accused goes through the entire system and “passes” he is ready to return to society.⁹ The criminal justice system is the major meeting place of the police and the citizen, and it is here that the clash between the exercise of police powers and the claim of rights by the citizen occurs. Hence, the AI can effectively assist to avoid such clash.

The word “justice” often conjures images of mystic superheroes saving the day from masked evil-doers. The field of criminal justice is full of everyday heroes, from police officers and forensic scientists to child welfare caseworkers, and even mere citizens. The field of criminal justice applies to law enforcement, the

¹³ See also: J. A. Inciardi, *Criminal Justice*, 7th ed. (Boston: Mc Graw Hill, 2004) 139.

¹⁴ *Black's Law Dictionary*, 8th ed. (USA: West Group Publishers, 1999) 381.

¹⁵ S 36(5) of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999(Fourth Alteration).

¹⁶ M C Onuegbulam, Extra judicial killing and its Challenges in the Nigerian Criminal Justice System, Unpublished LL.M dissertation 2013, Faculty of Law, University of Nigeria Enugu Campus.

¹⁷ The word “He” used in this work is inclusive of the female gender.

⁹ See also: S T Reid, *Crime and Criminology*, (Hinsdale Illinois: The Dryden Press, 1976) 260 (cited in G.O.S, Amadi, *Police Powers in Nigeria* (Nsukka: Afro-Orbis Publication Ltd., 2000) 32 – 33.

judicial process, juvenile justice, corrections, and criminal law.¹⁸ The criminal justice system thus needs strong force to keep the streets safe, the communities running, and stand up for what is right when things go wrong. Criminal justice therefore, involves the system of practices, policies, and agencies established by governments to maintain social order, deter and mitigate crime, and enforce laws. It encompasses various institutions and processes, including law enforcement, judicial systems, corrections, and rehabilitation programs. The goal of criminal justice is to ensure fair and just treatment for individuals accused of crimes, those who are victims of crimes, maintain public safety, uphold the rule of law, and provide opportunities for rehabilitation and reintegration into society for those who have been convicted of offenses.

Sentencing

By sentencing, it is “The judgment that a court formally pronounces after finding an offender guilty; or the punishment imposed on a criminal wrongdoer.”¹⁹ According to Oshodi²⁰, the word "sentence" is defined as a punishment given to a person convicted of a crime. A sentence is ordered by the Judge or Magistrate, based on the verdict of the Judge or Magistrate within the possible punishments set by the relevant Law whether Federal or State law. Douglas,²¹ defines “sentence” or “judgment” in legal parlance as denoting action of a Court of criminal jurisdiction formally declaring to an accused the legal consequences of the guilt to which he has confessed or of which he has been convicted. According to the Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary, a sentence is “the punishment given by a Court of law”.²² Okonkwo and Naish,²³ are of the view that if punishment is the object of criminal law, then sentencing is simply the way in which principles of punishment are applied to individual offenders. However, according to Bob Osamo²⁴ sentence is the pronouncement by the court, upon the accused person after his conviction in criminal prosecution, imposing the punishment to be inflicted. For Ekumanka²⁵ sentence is the act of imposing a penalty by the court on a wrongdoer for a crime or a wrongdoing. He emphasized the core relationship between sentencing and punishment because you cannot talk about sentencing without some form of punishment. Generally, a court’s sentence often ends with the punishment inflicted upon a convict at the end of the criminal trial. Once trial is over and the case against the accused is proved beyond reasonable doubt, the next step is to convict him for the offence and pronounce sentence on him and the adequate punishment as statutorily provided except where the court has any discretion to exercise. However, there could be aggravating or mitigating factors that could affect the sentence one way or the other. Also an *allocutus* on behalf of the convict may equally influence the judge’s leniency in sentencing if the court is so moved. An *allocutus* is a plea for the mitigation of the punishment rightly deserved by the accused person for the offence with which he was tried and convicted accordingly.²⁶ It is what the defendant has to say to show the court the reason the court should not impose maximum sentence on him at the conclusion of criminal trial. Sentencing and punishment are not strictly the same but they are interwoven.

¹⁸ National University. (n.d.). “What is Criminal Justice Administration”. National University. <https://www.nu.edu/blog/what-is-criminal-justice-administration>. accessed 22 March 2024.

¹⁹Black’s Law Dictionary 8th Edition

²⁰ O H Oshodi “Practice and Procedure under the Administration of Criminal Justice Act and Criminal Justice Laws” 2019 page 1 - 20. <https://nji.gov.ng/Paper-on-sentencing.pdf> accessed 21 February 2024.

²¹J Douglas “Administration of Criminal Justice: Sentencing Policy”. Conference of All Nigerian Judges.(1988) 3. <https://nji.gov.ng/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/Paper-on-sentencing.pdf> accessed 20 December 2023

²² A S Hornby, Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary, 8th ed. 1331.

²³Okonkwo, Naish, *Criminal Law in Nigeria*, 2nd Edition. Spectrum, Lagos, 2012. page 28

²⁴B Osamor, *Fundamentals of Criminal Procedure Law in Nigeria*, 1st Edition. Decsage Nig Ltd, Abuja, 2004. page 376.

²⁵D Ekumanka, *Criminology and Penology, a Nigerian Perspective*. New World Publishers, Jos, 2002. page 163

²⁶ Per Mohammad JSC in *Lucky v The State* (2016) LPELR 40541 sc.

Artificial Intelligence Bias

Ordinarily bias means inclination, prejudice. It is a systematic error in decision-making processes that results in unfair outcomes. Relating to Artificial Intelligence, bias can arise from various sources, including data collection, algorithm design,²⁷ and human interpretation. AI bias, also known as machine learning bias or algorithm bias, refers to AI systems that produce biased results that reflect and perpetuate human biases within a society, including historical and current social inequality.²⁸ The importance of fair hearing in any proceeding conducted by any court of law or tribunal cannot be over emphasised.²⁹ That right cannot be ignored.³⁰ There is need therefore to be very careful. Machine learning models, can learn and replicate patterns of bias present in the data used to train them, resulting in unfair or discriminatory outcome. Sources of bias in AI can arise from different stages of the machine learning pipeline, including data collection, algorithm design, and user interactions. There could be data bias, algorithmic bias, and user bias. Data bias occurs when the data used to train machine learning models is incomplete, leading to biased outputs. This can happen when data is collected from biased sources, or when the data is incomplete, missing important information, or contains errors. Algorithmic bias, on the other hand, occurs when the algorithms used in machine learning models have inherent biases that are reflected in their outputs. It is likely to occur when algorithms are based on biased assumptions or when they use biased criteria to make decisions. User bias occurs when the people using AI systems introduce their own biases or prejudices into the system, consciously or unconsciously³¹ and it can happen when users provide biased training data or when they interact with the system in ways that reflect their own biases.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) requires a huge amount of data for its training and AI algorithms may perpetuate biases present in the data used to train them. In other words, if the data is biased, the AI system will learn to be biased as well, and this can lead to discriminatory and unhealthy outcomes in areas such as profiling, crime investigation, sentencing, hiring etc.³² AI bias is the voluntary or involuntary imprinting of one or more human biases in one or more datasets. The model delivers biased results because of fallacious assumptions of the training data provided to the neural network. Once a model is trained through a biased dataset that has been affected by biased human decisions, historical/social inequities and/or ignored variables such as gender, race or national origin, the output comes with the consequence of unreliable results.³³ Ever since the Dartmouth Conference of the 1950s³⁴, AI has been

²⁷ Machine learning algorithms are sets of instructions that help people analyze and find meaning in complex data. It is a branch of artificial intelligence (AI) and computer science which focuses on the use of data and algorithms to imitate the way that humans learn, gradually improving its accuracy. In the context of criminal justice, it refers to computational models and techniques that enable computers to analyze data, identify patterns, and make predictions or decisions without explicit programming. These algorithms use statistical patterns and interactive learning to improve their performance over time. In criminal justice, it is applied to various tasks to enhance efficiency, accuracy, and objectivity. It is usually used interchangeably with Artificial Intelligence (AI), but a deep dive into computer programming would reveal that they are in fact different, though closely similar. While Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a simulated intelligence that replicates human behaviour, Machine learning (ML) is simply the study of computer algorithms that improve automatically through experience.

²⁸ Ferrera “. Fairness And Bias in Artificial Intelligence: A Brief Survey of Sources, Impacts, And Mitigation Strategies” (2023) <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/2304/2304.07683.pdf> accessed 2 December 2, 2023.

²⁹ NIMASA v NLNG & 2Ors (2019) BLP CA

³⁰ Chuwuma v FRN (2011)13 NWLR(Pt. 1264)391 @418.

³¹ Ferrera Ibid.

³² Funmirob, “When AI Meets Law: The Legal Implications of The Use of AI System”. 2023. <https://www.funmirobertsandco.com/2023/08/08/when-ai-meets-law>, accessed 30 December 2023.

³³ J. Manyika, J. Silberg, B. Presten, ”What Do We Do About the Biases in AI?” (Harvard Bus. Rev.) 2019. <https://nysba.org/bias-and-fairness-in-artificial-intelligenceDai>, accessed 30 December 2023.

³⁴ It took place in the year 1956 at Dartmouth College in New Hampshire, USA. The conference brought together researchers from seemingly disparate fields of study – Computer Science, Mathematics, Physics, and others – with the sole aim of exploring the potential of Synthetic Intelligence. See : R Anyoha, *The History of Artificial*

recognized as a legitimate field of study so that the early years of AI research focused on symbolic logic and rule-based systems. This involved manually programming machines to make decisions based on a set of predetermined rules. While these systems were useful in certain applications, they were of course limited in their ability to learn and adapt to new data. This poses a challenge in maintaining accuracy in judgment. However, deep learning³⁵ algorithms provides a glimpse of solution to this problem by enabling machines to automatically learn from large datasets and make predictions or decisions based on that learning.³⁶ Deep learning is a type of machine learning that uses artificial neural networks, which are modeled after the structure and function of the human brain.³⁷ It was not until after the rise of big data that deep learning became a major milestone in the history of AI. Thus, by leveraging machine learning algorithms, Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies are being utilized to assist judges in determining appropriate sentences and evaluate the likelihood of recidivism. AI algorithms analyze various factors, such as prior criminal history, offence severity, and demographic information to generate recommendations for sentencing, providing judges with additional information and support in determining sentences, leading to a more standardized approach.³⁸ Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies are also used for assessing the likelihood of an individual's future criminal behaviour, informing decisions related to parole, probation, or release conditions. Machine learning algorithms analyze historical data to identify patterns and risk factors associated with recidivism. Proponents claim that Artificial Intelligence (AI) can provide more accurate and objective risk assessments,³⁹ allowing for tailored interventions and reducing the risk of reoffending. Predictive analytics⁴⁰ could be employed by organizations and government bodies within the criminal justice system. Associating with Noble's⁴¹ view, one of the main concerns in the use of AI is the potential for discrimination against individuals or groups based on factors such as race, gender, age, or disability.

Obviously, when AI systems are biased, they can perpetuate existing inequalities and reinforce discrimination against marginalized groups. If bias in AI is not recognized, isolated and corrected, indeed the risks, repercussions and harm that will be meted to the criminal justice system, the global community and indeed to AI as a technology will be unimaginable. It will of course overcome the money and time savings AI was intended to realize through its original goals of problem-solving and prediction. Bias in AI has the potency of sowing prejudice against groups and ideas and limits the advancement of the technology. As Green⁴² rightly observed, if transparency is an issue, then human supervision is the last

Intelligence. Harvard University, Science in the News. 2017. sitn.hms.harvard.edu/flash/2017/hisoty-artificial-intelligence. Accessed 18 March 2024.

³⁵ This involved manually programming machines to make decisions based on a set of predetermined rules. While these systems were useful in certain applications, they were limited in their ability to learn and adapt to new data. These networks are made up of layers of interconnected nodes, each of which performs a specific mathematical function on the input data. The output of one layer serves as the input to the next, allowing the network to extract increasingly complex features from the data.

³⁶ R Anyoha, *The History of Artificial Intelligence*. Harvard University, Science in the News. 2017. sitn.hms.harvard.edu/flash/2017/hisoty-artificial-intelligence. Accessed 22 July 2024.

³⁷ E Gold "The History of Artificial Intelligence from the 1950s to Today". 2023. <https://www.freecodecamp.org/news/the-history-of-ai/#the-rise-of-big-data> accessed 1 December 2023

³⁸ A Hellweger, "Use of AI in Criminal Justice", Vol.1. (LexisNexis) 2023. <https://www.rahmanravelli.co.uk/assets/uploads/9434ffa1f/Use-of-AI-in-Criminal-Justice.pdf> accessed 1 December 2023

³⁹ A systematic process of evaluating the potential risks that may be involved in a projected activity or undertaking.

⁴⁰ The use of statistical algorithms and machine learning techniques to identify patterns in historical data and make predictions about future events or outcomes. Anticipating future outcomes by leveraging information from historical events.

⁴¹ S U Noble, *Algorithms of Oppression: How Search Engines Reinforce Racism*. Vol.1.(New York University Press, New York, USA 2018) 229.

⁴² B Green, "The Flows of Policies Requiring Human Oversight of Government Algorithms, 45 Journal of Computer Law & Security" 2022.

resort to control, manage and correct an algorithm. This is because algorithms are nothing more than a set of instructions for solving a problem or accomplishing a task. Parameters and options can be selected, or even manipulated at a later point in time, to reach certain results.

Expecting unbiased fairness in the real sense from a training algorithm may be asking for the impossible. Fairness is not inherent in a training algorithm that is fair by design. With respect to quality, the model can be black-box or transparent. Transparency in AI assumes paramount importance, as it holds the key to unlocking the full potential of AI while simultaneously ensuring its ethical, equitable, and responsible utilization.⁴³ With AI becoming part of criminal justice system, there is a growing need for the system to be more transparent. Not only that transparency fosters public trust and confidence in AI systems, it also supports compliance with legal and ethical standards, since it allows institutions to show that their AI systems adhere to established guidelines and regulations. This is because users and stakeholders can gain insights into how these technologies operate and arrive at decisions. The doubt is still there. Levey and Hagemann⁴⁴ argue that calls for algorithmic transparency in areas like criminal justice risk assessment are misguided because they fail to account for the opaque nature of advanced machine-learning techniques. Their argument is based on the fact that transparency requirements will not be effective with machine-learning techniques, because each is a "black box."; and transparency requirements are undesirable. They undermine intellectual property and market competition. Statutory obligations like the Freedom of Information Act 2011,⁴⁵ the jurisprudence of criminal procedure, constitution, and myriad of court precedents all set out additional rules and protections. The Freedom of Information Act 2011 provides for public access to public record and information. It obligates public institutions to maintain records and allow public access to information, among other things. It also establishes procedures for the achievement of these purposes. Notions of equity, predictability and, transparency are major concerns of the justice system. Transparency and accountability in the context of AI and criminal justice are crucial aspects that demand careful consideration and ethical scrutiny. As AI technologies play an increasingly prominent role in various aspects of the criminal justice system, including predictive policing, risk assessment, and decision-making processes, the need for transparency and accountability becomes paramount and yet remains a big challenge. The complex nature of many AI systems, often referred to as "black boxes," makes it difficult for stakeholders, including judicial officers, law enforcement officials, legal professionals, and the public, to understand how decisions are reached. Establishing clear accountability mechanisms requires transparency in the design, training, and deployment of AI systems to ensure that biases, errors, or unintended consequences can be identified and addressed. There has to be a framework of oversight and responsibility in order to achieve accountability in the criminal justice system. This of course involves establishing clear lines of responsibility for the development and deployment of AI systems that are compatible with the principles inherent in the criminal justice system. Legal and ethical frameworks should be in place to hold individuals, organizations, and AI developers accountable for the consequences of AI-generated decisions outside judicial process.

⁴³ R Kumar, "AI and Transparency: Importance of transparency and accountability in AI decision-making processes" 2023. <https://www.importance-of-transparency-and-accountability-in-ai-decision-making-processes>, accessed 20 June 2024.

⁴⁴C Levey, R. Hagemann, "Algorithms With Minds of Their Own How do we ensure that artificial intelligence is accountable?" 2017. <https://www.wsj.com/articles/algorithms-with-minds-of-their-own-1510521093> accessed 20 June 2024

⁴⁵In Nigeria for example.

4. Artificial intelligence in Criminal Justice System Advantages and Disadvantage

Obviously, Artificial Intelligence (AI) is programmed to exhibit a unique intelligence that is quick to comprehend and seems intuitive. It demonstrates sharpness and acuity in its ability to analyze, synthesize, distinguish, select, and adapt to various situations. It is acknowledged that Artificial Intelligence (AI) is useful in predictive policing, efficient case management, evidence analysis, particularly in forensic science, sentencing and risk assessment and it can promote rehabilitation and reduce recidivism rates.⁴⁶ However, in employing AI, it must be ensured that we are promoting a safe, secure and trustworthy Artificial Intelligence that operates in compliance with the laws and ethics of criminal justice without posing undue risks to justice, fairness, and without compromising either the rights of the victim or the accused person, not even the State. It is all about the ability of a tool or some device (robot) to perform some activities that need intelligence, such as actual reasoning and self-correction. The fact remains that there is no AI without human intelligence since the AI-enabled system depends on the knowledge embedded in it from human knowledge. It is the simulation of human intelligence in machines that are programmed to think, learn, and problem-solve like humans, thereby encompassing a wide range of technologies and techniques that enable computers and systems to perform tasks that typically require human intelligence. In the legal arena, AI seems to have progressed from enhancing legal research and case analysis to streamlining contract review and automating mundane tasks, including reshaping how legal professionals deliver services and interact with their clients. So much so that AI-powered legal research platforms have become essential tools for lawyers. However, their application in the criminal justice system is not without implications. From predictive policing to the analysis of court transcripts, AI technologies are being deployed to enhance the efficiency, accuracy, and fairness of criminal justice processes.⁴⁷ Over time, advancements in machine learning, natural language processing, and big data analytics have led to more sophisticated applications. Today, AI is utilized in various aspects of criminal justice, including predicting policing, Facial Recognition, Risk Assessment Tools, Automated Case Management.

When it comes to predictive policing, it involves the use of AI algorithms to analyze historical crime data and predict future incidents. These algorithms can identify hotspots for criminal activity, allowing law enforcement agencies to allocate resources more effectively. It enables resource optimization, crime prevention by increasing police presence in predicted hot-spots. It also promotes data-driven decision, reduces reliance on subjective judgment and promotes objective decision-making. However, there could be biases because AI systems can perpetuate existing biases present in historical crime data. This may lead to disproportionate targeting of certain communities and populations. Furthermore, increased surveillance and data collection can infringe on individual privacy rights thereby creating privacy concerns.⁴⁸

Also, facial recognition technology uses AI to match facial features from images or video footage with databases of known faces. The technology is widely used for identifying suspects, verifying identities, and locating missing persons. Introducing it into the criminal justice system will be beneficial in helping to maintain surveillance by monitoring public spaces for known offenders, assisting in the identification of suspects from security camera footage. It will equally enhance security measures in courts, police cells and correctional facilities. However, some inherent ethical and legal concerns are obvious. Research has shown that facial recognition systems can exhibit bias, particularly against minority groups, leading to wrongful identifications.⁴⁹ There is therefore the need for stringent regulations to govern the use of facial recognition technology to prevent misuse and adequately handle possible issues regarding consent and the right to privacy. Furthermore, risk assessment tools use AI to evaluate the risk of reoffending, which informs decisions regarding bail, sentencing, and parole. These tools analyze various factors, including criminal history, socio-

⁴⁶ Imhoff & Associates, PC, *The Impact of AI on the Criminal Justice System: A Technological Revolution*, Oct 3, 2023

⁴⁷ Ahmed Banafa, *The Use of AI in the Criminal Justice Field*, 24 July 2024.

⁴⁸ Ahmed Banafa, *Ibid*.

⁴⁹ *Ibid*. See also: A Lensen, M Betker, "We Built Algorithm that Predict the Length of Court Sentences - could AI play a role in the Justice System". 2022. <https://theconversation.com/we-built-an-algorithm-that-predicts-the-length-of-court-sentences-could-ai-play-a-role-in-the-justice-system-193300> accessed 3 April 2024.

economic status, and psychological profiles. Thus, it can help to provide judges with data-driven insights, promote consistency in judicial decisions thereby reducing disparities. It promotes efficiency and helps to streamline the decision-making process, saving time and resources. However, there could be possibility of bias and unfair outcome. Transparency may not even be assured. This is because these tools can inherit biases from the data they are trained on, potentially leading to unfair outcomes. Also, the proprietary nature of many algorithms reveals that their inner workings are not always transparent.

The use of AI for automated case management will be beneficial in streamlining legal processes. AI-driven case management systems automate various administrative tasks, such as scheduling, document management, and workflow coordination.⁵⁰ These systems improve the efficiency and effectiveness of legal processes, they reduce the administrative burden on legal professionals, minimize human errors in document handling and case tracking and improve access to case information for all stakeholders. However, It could be somehow complex to ensure compatibility with legacy systems and it requires training for legal professionals to effectively use new technologies.⁵¹ There is also need for data security. Thus, protecting sensitive legal information from cyber threats is of great importance. Research has shown that using artificial intelligence in court proceedings could be of great benefit in legal research, predictive analytics in litigation, virtual legal assistants etc. AI tools are said to have the capacity of rapidly analyzing vast amounts of legal documents and case law to provide relevant information, which can aid lawyers in case preparation and research. AI can predict the likely outcome of litigation based on historical data, thereby helping legal teams to strategize effectively. AI-driven virtual assistants can support lawyers by managing schedules, sending reminders, and even drafting basic legal documents⁵². However, amidst these benefits are obvious ethical and social implications. The deployment of AI in criminal justice must be guided by principles of fairness and equity. There is need to address biases in AI systems as it is critical to prevent the perpetuation of existing inequalities. Transparency in AI algorithms and accountability for their decisions are essential. Stakeholders have to understand how decisions are made and have recourse in cases of errors or biases. Transparency and ethical use of AI will help to build public trust in AI technologies.

Traditional methods of sentencing in the criminal justice system have historically relied on the law, judges' discretion, legal guidelines, and precedent. However, these approaches sometimes come with inherent limitations that impact the fairness and effectiveness of the justice system. Additionally, traditional methods of sentencing often overlook crucial individual factors like Socio-economic background that could influence criminal behavior and the appropriate punishment. Furthermore, the focus of traditional sentencing methods on punitive measures rather than rehabilitative measures has contributed to the issue of overcrowded prisons. Harsh sentences, particularly for non-violent offenses, have led to a disproportionate number of individuals incarcerated, straining prison resources and limiting the effectiveness of rehabilitation programs. Instead of addressing the underlying issues, lengthy incarcerations often exacerbate problems, making it more challenging for individuals to reintegrate into society upon release. Racial and socio-economic disparities are another concerning aspect of the effect of traditional sentencing methods. Studies have shown that individuals from marginalized communities, particularly people of color and those with low socio-economic status, are more likely to receive harsher sentences for similar offenses compared to their counterparts from more privileged backgrounds. These disparities highlight the systemic biases ingrained in traditional sentencing practices.

Amidst these growing limitations in traditional sentencing is the urgent call for innovation in criminal justice system. Emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence, offer the potential to address these issues. AI-driven algorithms can analyze a vast array of factors, including individual backgrounds and crime contexts, to provide judges with comprehensive and unbiased information for sentencing decisions. By employing AI, the justice system can move toward a more equitable, consistent, and individualised approach to justice, fairness, and sentencing, fostering rehabilitation and reducing recidivism rates especially in the absence of AI bias.

⁵⁰ Ahmed Banafa, *The Use of AI in the Criminal Justice Field*, 24 July 2024. See also: Blog Post "Smart Courts and the Push for Technological Innovation in China's Judicial System" <http://www.csis.org/blogs/new-perspective-asia/smart-courts-and-technological-innovation-chinas-judicial-system> . accessed 20 March 2024.

⁵¹ *ibid.*

⁵² A Lensen, M Betker, *ibid.* See also: Ahmed Banafa ,*ibid.*

Furthermore, innovative approaches should prioritize community-based rehabilitation programs, counseling services, and educational opportunities for offenders. Thus, by addressing the root causes of criminal behavior and providing necessary support systems, these approaches can contribute significantly to reducing crime rates and building safer communities. Obviously, embracing technology and adopting rehabilitative strategies can pave the way for a more just, fair, and effective system that benefits not only individuals within the system but also society as a whole. In sentencing and parole decisions for example, AI algorithms assess defendants' backgrounds, criminal histories, and offense details, providing judges with data-driven insights to support their decisions.

AI also plays a role in prison management, monitoring inmate behavior and helping in resource allocation and rehabilitation programs. Notably, Artificial Intelligence (AI) is quickly becoming an important technology even in fraud detection.⁵³ Thus, Internet companies like PayPal⁵⁴ NG stay ahead of fraud attempts by using volumes of data to continuously train their fraud detection algorithms to predict and recognize anomalous patterns and to learn to recognize new patterns.⁵⁵ Recently, researchers at the University of Leon, in north-west Spain, were reported to be training neural networks to detect clues left at a crime scene.⁵⁶ This is done by feeding thousands of images from crime scenes into the computer so the machine learning algorithms will know what they need to detect. This includes possible patterns used by criminals in different situations, which could connect all of the crimes to one person. For example, if a burglary took place, there are all kinds of objects that could be left behind by the robbers which could be used to connect them to other robberies in the area.

5. Compatibility of Artificial Intelligence with Justice, Fairness and Legal Ethics in The Nigerian Criminal Justice System

As laudable and exciting as the use of AI in criminal justice System may be, its compatibility with principles of fairness, justice, and ethics in a fragile democracy like Nigeria may appear as remote as it could be a nightmare in the absence of compelling judicial discipline and commitment which the system craves for. There are some serious legal concerns that has to be considered when it comes to using algorithms to make decisions that can have life-altering consequences e.g. wrongful sentencing. The legal implications of integrating artificial intelligence (AI) in criminal justice are profound and multifaceted. It could be a plus on one side and a minus at the other end as already discussed. One of the primary concerns is the potential for bias in AI algorithms. If these algorithms are trained on biased data, they can perpetuate and reinforce existing prejudices within the criminal justice system. This raises serious legal questions on equal protection under the law and fairness in procedures, criminal justice and justice delivery. Courts need to ensure that AI systems used in processes such as sentencing, do not discriminate against certain demographic groups and that the outcomes are consistent with legal principles of fairness and non-discrimination. Transparency and accountability are also critical legal issues in AI-driven sentencing. The obscurity of AI algorithms often referred to as the "black box" problem, raises challenges relating to due process. Parties and especially defendants have the constitutional right to understand the evidence used against them and be able to defend himself.⁵⁷ When AI systems are involved in generating evidence or determining sentences, it is essential for the legal system to establish mechanisms that allow defendants and their legal representatives to comprehend the algorithms' outputs. It is necessary to ensure transparency to uphold the principle of due process and the right to a fair trial. Issues relating to bias, transparency, due process, Justice and legal accountability, must be responsibly addressed. It is essential for legal systems to adapt and develop comprehensive frameworks that

⁵³A Jaoker "Artificial Intelligence in Fraud Detection" Evision Blog 2017

⁵⁴Paypal NG is the faster, safer way to send money and make an online payment or set up a merchant account.

⁵⁵E Knorr "How Paypal Beats the Bad Guys with Machine Learning" Ahead of the Curve, InfoWorld 2015, accessed 2 December 2023.

⁵⁶D Fernández-Alonso, J. Fernandez-Alonso, M. T. Garcia-Ordas, "Conventional Neural Networks for Accurate Identification of Mining Remains from UAV-Derived Images" 2023. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/375746221_Conventional_neural_networks_for_accurate_identification_of_mining_remains_from_UAV-derived_images accessed 7 December 2023.

⁵⁷CFRN S 36(6)(a),(b),(c),(d).

safeguard the rights of individuals involved in AI-assisted criminal justice, and ensure that these processes align with established legal principles and standards.

Artificial Intelligence (AI), no doubt poses clear risks when lawyers use them without understanding their limitations. Recently, an attorney incurred the wrath of a New York Federal Judge for submitting a brief with cases invented by ChatGPT⁵⁸. The court imposed \$5,000 fines on two lawyers and a law firm in an unprecedented instance in which ChatGPT was blamed for their submission of fictitious legal research in an aviation injury claim⁵⁹. According to the Judge they acted in bad faith.

Most recently, The United Nations General Assembly on 21 March 2024 also recognized AI systems' potential to accelerate and enable progress towards reaching the 17 Sustainable Development Goals. The General Assembly adopted a landmark resolution on the promotion of safe, secure and trustworthy artificial intelligence (AI) system that will also benefit sustainable development. In adopting the United States-led draft resolution without a vote, the General Assembly also highlighted the respect, protection and promotion of human rights in the design, development, deployment and the use of AI. The General Assembly as a matter of emphasis called on all Member States and stakeholders to refrain from or cease the use of artificial intelligence systems that are impossible to operate in compliance with international human rights law or that pose undue risks to the enjoyment of human rights. It emphasised that the same rights that people have offline must also be protected online, including throughout the life cycle of artificial intelligence systems.⁶⁰

In Nigeria, the use of AI technology in the criminal justice system in a dependent judiciary and fragile democracy will be a very big minus to principles of fairness, justice and ethics. However, it will be a plus when the judiciary and entire criminal justice system learn to be independent and free from the shackles of political powers. Nonetheless, technology should not be despised simply because it can be abused and misused so that it is better to face the real limitations rather than 'imagined implications' of AI Technology. Granted that software programmes can malfunction and cause serious harm without being considered as "entities" subject to criminal liability. Innovations like the AI could revolutionize the legal profession, and a plethora of legal technology start-ups. Large language models such as Open AI's ChatGPT, Bing Chat, and Google Bard, are designed to comprehend large volumes of data, but their effectiveness can be hampered by poor-quality scans and documents in languages not commonly used in their training. Thus, employing Artificial Intelligence demands a paradigm shift from traditional search engine queries and terms. Lawyers need to engage in dialogue with these models, and have good mastery of the workings of AI before its application. Despite implications and compatibility challenges, the benefits of AI Technology in justice administration cannot be over emphasised.

On the international arena, recently, on 1st January 2024, the Russian Federation launched one of the biggest air attacks on a number of Ukrainian cities, including Kyiv. Prior to this, on 28th May 2023 it was

⁵⁸Benjamin Weiser; *Here's What Happens When Your Lawyer Uses ChatGPT*

<http://www.nytimes/23/5/27/nyregion/avianca-airlines-lawsuit-chatGPT>, Accessed 10 April 2024.

⁵⁹Roberto Mata v Airline Avianca. <http://www.nytimes/23/5/27/nyregion/avianca-airlines-lawsuit-chatGPT>, The lawsuit began like so many others: A man named Roberto Mata sued the airline Avianca, saying he was injured when a metal serving cart struck his knee during a flight to Kennedy International Airport in New York. When Avianca asked a Manhattan federal judge to toss out the case, Mr. Mata's lawyers vehemently objected, submitting a 10-page brief that cited more than half a dozen relevant court decisions. There was *Martinez v Delta Air Lines case No. 2.00-CV filed on 02/08/2021*, *Zicherman v Korean Air Lines and Co.* 516 U.S. 217 (1996) and, of course, *Varghese v. China Southern Airlines*, 925 F.3d 1339 (11th Cir with its learned discussion of federal law and "the tolling effect of the automatic stay on a statute of limitations. There was just one hitch: No one — not the airline's lawyers, not even the judge himself — could find the decisions or the quotations cited and summarized in the brief. That was because ChatGPT had invented everything. The lawyer who created the brief, Steven A. Schwartz of the firm Levidow, Levidow & Oberman, threw himself on the mercy of the court on Thursday, saying in an affidavit that he had used the artificial intelligence program to do his legal research — "a source that has revealed itself to be unreliable.

⁶⁰UN News: A view of the General Assembly in session. (file) <https://news.un.org/en/story/2024/03/1147831>, accessed 17 April 2024.

reported⁶¹ that Russian Federation launched 54 drones on the city of Kyiv overnight. The air defence systems shot down 52 of these drones. Russia, on 23 January 2024 launched a “massive” airstrike on the cities of Kyiv and Kharkiv, firing 41 missiles. The air defences shot down 21 of these missiles. As a result of this military operation, it was reported that a number of buildings in a historic neighbourhood where a famous monastery is located caught fire. Individuals living in Kyiv, a city which was one of the most heavily bombed cities in Ukraine in 2023, reported suffering considerable psychological toll as a result of regular aerial bombardments. Now, in order to evaluate whether a particular military operation or operations on Kyiv consisting of air bombing breached the prohibition in Article 51(2) of the Additional Protocol to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts (Protocol I) 1977, known as API 1977, one needs to know what military objectives were in the area. Article 51 (2) of Additional Protocol I 1977 prohibits “acts or threats of violence with the primary purpose to spread terror among the civilian population.” Artificial intelligence (AI) can be a tool which members of the international legal community and civil society can use to supplement their own analysis regarding whether the military commander launched an attack or series of attacks with the aim of spreading terror among the civilian population in a situation, such as the air bombardment of Kyiv. It is possible to use AI as a tool to aid the assessment of the extent and degree the conduct of a particular military operation deviates from how a reasonable commander would have planned and carried out the military operation in question.⁶² However, AI should not and does not substitute for the traditional approach to evaluation and investigation but should not be used to compromise international humanitarian law or human rights in any way.

6. CONCLUSION

The criminal justice system is a complex and dynamic entity that strives to maintain public safety, uphold the rule of law, and ensure fair treatment for all individuals. However, integrating AI also raises important questions and challenges that the criminal justice system must carefully address. While the crave to integrate AI Technology into criminal justice system is compelling, effort must be made to ensure that integrating AI into the criminal justice system remains a plus to the principles of fairness, justice and legal ethics. The Core values of criminal justice must not be compromised. It stands to be recognized that in the resolution of human conflicts or disputes, the essence of conflict or dispute resolution process, is that justice be done; whether it is taken to the subject or the subject is brought to justice, justice must be served. To qualify as justice, trial must include hearing and the hearing must be impartial, dispassionate (independent), just, non-discriminatory, open minded, evenhanded, fair-minded, reasonable and rational. These are the import of the provision for fair hearing in section 36 of the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (Fifth Alteration) and indeed in various legal statutes for criminal justice which any framework for adoption of AI in criminal justice system should not ignore. Justice is not just about the result but the fairness of the process of hearing. Therefore, any AI Technology introduced into the Nigerian criminal justice system has to be compatible with the principles of fairness, justice and legal ethics which are distinguishing characteristics of criminal justice.

⁶¹ BBC NEWS Report.

⁶² Paragraph 50. See also: *Tetyana (Tanya) Krupiy*, What role artificial intelligence could play in evaluating the compliance of military operations with international humanitarian law: The case study of the conduct of hostilities in Ukraine, Blog of the *European Journal of International Law*, February 23, 2024